

SYNCRETISM AND POLYFUNCTIONALITY OF AUXILIARY VERBS IN INFLECTIONAL AND AGGLUTINATIVE LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article discusses about the issues on auxiliary verbs in agglutinative and inflectional languages. In particular, the syncretic nature of modal verbs in English and auxiliary verbs in Uzbek is highlighted, and their polyfunctional properties are analysed using the example of the verbs **can** and **could**, **bil** and **ol**. The Uzbek language, which belongs to agglutinative languages, does not have a group of modal verbs. In a number of sources it is noted that non-categorical forms of the verb are divided into two types, the first group includes functional forms of the verb, and the second group includes modal forms of the verb.

Key words: auxiliary verbs, modal verbs, primary auxiliaries, incomplete verbs, linking verbs, syncretism, polyfunctionality.

In the world linguistics, verbs are mainly divided into two groups, such as full or lexical verbs and auxiliary or modal verbs. Declerck writes about the characteristics of not full verbs in English and divides them into two groups: “Auxiliaries have little or no lexical meaning. They are ‘helper’ verbs, in the sense that they help to form complex verb forms. In doing so they express either a grammatical notion (like ‘passive’, ‘progressive’ or ‘tense’) or one or more modal ideas. This is not to say that auxiliaries are devoid of meaning, but their meanings are more schematic (i. e. more ‘skeletal’, more ‘abstract’, less ‘full’) than those of lexical verbs. Within the auxiliaries we can make a distinction between two classes: grammatical auxiliaries and modal auxiliaries. The former, which are sometimes referred to as ‘primary auxiliaries’, have a purely grammatical function” (Declerck, 2006:19). Among such grammatical auxiliary verbs are the verb *have*, which is used to form the perfect tense, the verb *be*, which forms continuous aspect forms, the verb *be*, which is used to form relative forms, and the verb *do*, which is called a

periphrastic auxiliary verb, and used in situations where a verb combination requires an auxiliary verb and there is no auxiliary verb.

Palmer expresses the following points about auxiliary verbs: “Although the ultimate test of an auxiliary verb must be in terms of its syntagmatic relations with other verbs in the verb phrase, it is a striking and, perhaps, fortunate characteristic of English that the auxiliary verbs are marked by what Huddleston (1976:333) has referred to as their 'NICE' properties. This refers to the fact that they occur with negation, inversion, 'code' and emphatic affirmation (NICE being an acronym formed from the initial consonants of these terms)” (Palmer, 1988:14). He also makes such points about the classification of auxiliary verbs: “Although the discussion so far has been concerned with auxiliaries as a single class, there is an important distinction between the primary auxiliaries, and the secondary or modal auxiliaries (or simply the 'modals'). BE and HAVE plus DO in its special functions are primary auxiliaries: WILL, SHALL, CAN, MAY, MUST, OUGHT, DARE and NEED are the modals (the last two may also be full verbs)” (Palmer, 1988:26).

On the site aimed at developing academic writing skills in English auxiliary verbs are described in the following way: “Auxiliary verbs offer a variety of perspectives on the event, state, etc. denoted by the main verb in the verb phrase. Traditionally, auxiliary verbs are divided into three subclasses; primary auxiliary verbs, modal auxiliary verbs, and marginal (or semi-) auxiliary verbs. The division is based partly on meaning and partly on grammatical properties of the three types” (<https://www.awelu.lu.se/language/selective-mini-grammar/verb-phrases/auxiliary-verbs>). It is obvious that this source divides auxiliary verbs into three groups. The first group is the primary auxiliaries as given in the abovementioned literature, including *do*, *be* and *have*, the second group includes verbs such as *can-could*, *may-might*, *shall-should*, *will-would*, *must*, and the third group is the marginal (semi) auxiliary verbs that include the verbs *dare* and *need*, which Palmer states as full verbs.

"Concise Oxford Dictionary of Linguistics" defines auxiliary verbs and their classification as Declerck and Palmer: "A verb belonging to a small class which syntactically accompanies other verbs: opp. lexical verb, full verb. E.g. *could* and *have* are auxiliaries in *He could have done it*. The first belongs to a class of modal verbs used only with other verbs or in elliptical sentences where a verb is understood. The second is an auxiliary related to the past participle (*done*); distinguished as such from *have* as a full verb, e.g. in *I have the answer*" (Matthews, 2003:21). Although this definition provides a more precise description of modal verbs, the interpretation of other auxiliary words is not presented there.

In the Uzbek linguistics, auxiliary and incomplete verbs are distinguished besides full verbs. Many researchers have put forward the opinion that auxiliary verbs are auxiliary verbs that combine with verbs and express various additional meanings, verbs that are used to add a certain grammatical meaning to the lexical meaning of the verb lexeme.

Jalolova, who analyzed the classification of verbs in the English and Uzbek languages in a comparative aspect, divides them into independent and non-independent verbs according to the independent meaning of the verbs. She makes the following comments about non-independent verbs: "Non-independent verbs do not have an independent meaning; they cannot act as part of a sentence and serve as independent verbs. They are used to express different grammatical meanings, often serving to add modal, aspect, duration, tense, voice, positiveness-negativeness, taxis, and other grammatical meanings to the main verb. Independent verbs have an important grammatical importance, their number is very small, so this type of verbs is considered as a closed system. Through a comparative study of independent verbs, it was found that they are completely different from each other in their own way in both languages. In English: linking, auxiliary and modal verbs; In the Uzbek language: linking, auxiliary (incomplete) and helping verbs (Jalolova, 2019:15).

Palmer lists the following features that distinguish modal verbs from primary auxiliary verbs: "[i] Only the primary auxiliaries have -s forms: *is*, *has* and *does*:

there are no modal forms **wills*, **shalls*, **cans*, **mays*, **musts* and **oughts*. *Dares* and *needs* exist, but are forms of the full verbs DARE and NEED and not the auxiliaries. [ii] The modals have no non-inite forms; they therefore cannot co-occur, and are restricted to initial position in the verb phrase. There are no forms such as **can may go*, **must can go*, etc. By contrast BE and HAVE (but not DO) have finite forms and so can co-occur and can occur other than in initial position in the verb phrase: *has been singing*, *has been hurt*, *must be singing*, *mst have sung*. There are, however, strict limitations on their co-occurrence, with a restriction to the bare infinitives be and have (the to-ininitives after OUGHT), the *-ing* form *being* and the *-en* form *been*.” (Palmer, 1988:26).

Greenbaum emphasizes the following aspects that distinguish modal verbs from primary auxiliaries: “The modals differ from the primary auxiliaries in several ways: 1. They do not have an -s form for the third person singular present: *He maybe there*. *She can drive*. 2. They do not have non-finite forms and therefore must be the first verb in the verb phrase. 3. Their past forms are often used to refer to present or future time: *He might be there now*. *She could drive my car tomorrow*” (Greenbaum, 1996:154). It can be seen that Palmer’s and Greenbaum's views on the differences between modal verbs and auxiliary verbs are quite close to each other, both researchers note that modal verbs are not marked with an suffix typical for the third person present tense form, and also because they have only a finite form, they are used at the beginning of the verb combination, i.e. in the first position. Palmer states that modal verbs are not used together. Another characteristic of modal verbs put forward by Greenbaum is that their past tense forms refer to the present or future tense. In the sentence *He might be there now*, the researcher gave an example, the verb *might* is the past tense form of the modal verb, but the word *now* in the sentence shows that the action refers to the present tense. In the second example (*She could drive my car tomorrow*), the word *could*, which is the past tense form of the modal verb *can*, is used with the adverb *tomorrow*, indicating that the time of the action is in the future.

Declerck considers the verbs *can, could, may, might, must, shall, should, ought to, will, and would* as modal verbs and relates the difference between primary auxiliary verbs and modal auxiliaries to their semantic aspect. The researcher emphasizes that modal auxiliary verbs are used to express desire, possibility, permission, need, purpose, obligation, assumption, ability, certainty, etc. He mentions that modal verbs are semantically different from primary auxiliary verbs, that is, they serve to add lexical meaning without performing a grammatical function. Also, “However, they still have less concrete, and hence more widely applicable, meanings than most lexical verbs” (Declerck, 2006:19).

Tursunov et al. write about auxiliary verbs the following: “Auxiliary verbs are combined with independent verbs and make up forms with different meanings: *ukib chikdi, chuchib ketdi, ukib beradi, ukiy boshladi*. The auxiliary verbs *kil, et, ayla, bul* mainly serve to form compound verbs: *yordam kilmok, hurmat kilmok, e'tibor bermok, vafo aylamok, katta bulmok*.. Incomplete verbs (*edi, ekan, emish, sometimes, erur*), which are considered as a type of auxiliary verbs, are mainly used to form the analytical tense forms of the verb (like *kelgan edim, kelayotgan ekansan, kelar emish, kelib edim, kelmikda ekan*) and as a linking part of a noun predicate... For this task, the auxiliary verb *bul* is also used” (Tursunov et al, 1992:316). Rakhmatullaev, one of the authors of this textbook, states almost 20 years later the following: “Historically, the verb *er-* had existed, and later this verb lost its lexical meaning and, at the same time, the feature of creating various forms from it. Considering these two cases, this verb is called an incomplete verb. There is no any incomplete verb in the modern Uzbek language, but there are the affixoids *edi, ekan, emish* that formed from the base of the verb *e-*” and emphasizes the idea that there is no imperfect verb in the modern Uzbek language.

Jalolova studied conjunctions and auxiliary verbs in English and Uzbek and made the following conclusions: "1. Linking verbs make up a noun predicate mainly together with nouns (*I am a teacher*), adjectives (*She is beautiful*), numbers (*It is 9 o'clock*), pronouns (*It is me*) and words that express the meaning of the situation

(statives, adlinks). According to the results of the analysis of linking verbs, the following types were determined: pure (*to be*); special (expressing sense: *look, seem, appear, feel, taste*; not expressing sense: *become, get, grow, remain, keep, turn, go, run*). Moreover, linking verbs can express an independent meaning; such linking verbs are in use until now as they were formed from independent verbs... In Uzbek, some linguists combine these two terms (linking and auxiliary verbs) into one term and call it “incomplete verb”. they use Accordingly, in the Uzbek language, incomplete verbs are *edi, emish, ekan*. It was also observed that in the Uzbek language, a non-independent verb can become a linking verb or an auxiliary verb depending on the context... 2. Auxiliary verbs are added to independent verbs and form their categorial forms. Such forms are considered analytic forms and have one independent verb and one to four (in English) auxiliary verbs” (Jalolova, 2019:15).

In his research work, Ergashev considered the functional typology of verbs in the English language, in which he distinguished the main verb, connecting verb, auxiliary verb and modal verb. This is the definition of a linking verb that is the object of his research: “A linking verb is a functional type of the verb, and is a linguistic unit that lost its lexical meaning in whole or in part, functionally serves to connect nouns or substantivized linguistic elements in the language to each other in speech through a predicative relationship. It includes all the grammatical, semantic and functional properties of the verb” (Ergashev, 2020:13-14)

Below we will analyze the polyfunctional aspects of the incomplete verbs *edi, ekan* and *emish*.

The imperfect verb *edi* usually forms the past tense:

Hatto uzimizdan chikkan Uzakov degan mukhbir ham “Amerikasini ham kurdik”, degan makola yozgan edi (U.Hoshimov)

In the sentence above the incomplete verb is used to refer to the past with the verb predicate.

Kelgan odam dadasi edi (A.Korjavov).

In this sentence, this incomplete verb is used in the predicate represented by the noun.

Furthermore, this incomplete verb expresses the existence of another action or situation that occurred before a certain action in compound sentences, and it also performs the function of connecting the subordinate clause to the main clause in such sentences:

Alijon Latofatning shu iltimosiga javoban “bugun ham taklif kilsa, nima deb javob beraman” degan mulohazada edi, koridoorda eshitilgan oyok kiyimi ovozi bilan xayoli bulinib ketdi.

Also, the incomplete verb *edi* is used with verbs in the imperative-optative mood, and in this case, the meaning of past is noticeable:

Unaka olifta bulsa, kelmasin edi.

Being the most productive in terms of functions, the incomplete verb *ekan* is used when the existence of an action or state has become clear now:

Insof bilan aytganda, bifshteksi mazaligina ekan (U.Hoshimov).

It is used to express that the subject understood by it is the cause of an event:

Uz ikhtiyorimiz bilan shu vazifani zimmamizga olgan ekanmiz, buynimizga olgan yukni yarim yulda tashlash biz uchun order, aybdir.

In the following sentence, the incomplete verb *ekan* is used to express the meaning of conditionality:

Uchinchdan, shu odating bor ekan, nega oldindan aytib kuymading? (U.Hoshimov)

Also, this incomplete verb can express the meaning of continuity:

Shahodat mufti savagich kalamini bir-ikki davotga tikib olgach, kuzi qogozda ekan, javob berdi.

We can also see that the incomplete verb *ekan* has the function of indicating that one state or action is not an obstacle to another state:

Hali bitta Fosih afandi ekan-u, mingta Fosih afandi kelib guvohlikka utganda ham...khayr, bu gapni kuyaylik.

In addition, this incomplete verb can indicate how a certain action is performed:

Ha, ha, – dedi Yuldoshboy gazabidan titrar ekan.

Hojiev describes the following cases about the functions of the incomplete verb *ekan* in interrogative sentences:

1) The requested thing, action, etc. are not known to the speaker and the listener first, but then they become known: *Kayerda ekan?*

2) If what is being asked is known to the listener, then such meanings as surprise, wonder are expressed:

Bordi-yu, mashinani tukhtadigan militsionerning uzini kastdan urib, yikitib utsa-chi, unda nima buladi? – Unisini bilmadim... Kanaka shofyor ekan u dovyurak.

3) There are cases where the question is not expressed in interrogative sentences with *ekan*, in cases a) when the speaker does not know the object, action, etc., he is unfamiliar with it: *Uning kuzi tunka ustida turgan chit kuylakka tushdi. Bu kimniki ekan?* b) when the object or action is in the past tense, such meanings as the speaker did not know before and is regretting now: “*Rozi emasman” degan gapni ilgarirok aytsam nima ekan?*” (Hojiev, 1973:74)

The incomplete verb *emish* is rarely used in the modern Uzbek. We will analyze its functions below.

Eshitishimcha, Toshkentdan, Bukhorodan, Kukondan va boshqa joylardan bir kancha yigit-kizlar Moskvaga ukishga ketgan emish.

In this sentence this verb refers to the meaning that the speaker has known this information from somebody else.

Seni kara-ya! Uning kuli usha kuniyok tuzalib ketgan, “vrach” emish-a...

In the example above, the incomplete verb *emish* is used to express displeasure.

At this point, we think it is appropriate to discuss the syncretic nature of auxiliary verbs in English, especially the verb *be*.

“It’s bad for children,” said old Cotter, “because their mind are so impressionable” (J.Joyce)

In the example above this verb is functioning as a linking verb in two positions (as a contracted *is* and a full *are*)

He was sitting on the black chair.

The verb *was* in this sentence is used to form a continuous verb.

An invitation to dinner was soon afterwards dispatched (J.Austen).

In the sentence the verb *was* is used to form a passive verb

Moreover, the verb *be* can be used as a modal verb. In these cases after forms of this verb an infinitive with *to* is used and it may perform a function of expressing one of two meanings:

The train was to leave at 8.

In this sentence the modal verb is performing to refer an action which should have occurred, been defined before.

I’m to work in London next year.

In the sentence above the linking verb is functioning to express the future reference.

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